

Abusive Supervision and Employees OCB: An Important Role of Psychological Contract Fulfilment and Trust in Leadership

Maha El halouat & Shimin Liu

Abstract:

Contemporary organizations need a workforce who can work more enthusiastically to compete in the market. This study synthesizes leadership paradigms for the purpose of exploring possible ways of influencing organizational citizenship behaviors to increase the functioning of organizations. Further, we test for the underlying mechanisms, psychological contract fulfilment between leadership style and employees organizational citizenship behaviors. In addition, we examined for the moderating role of trust in leader between leadership style and organizational citizenship behaviors. Collecting data from 436 employees from the agriculture sector organizations in Morocco, we found that abusive leadership has a negative relationships with organizational citizenship behaviors. Using SPSS and AMOS as a statistical tools, our findings further confirms the mediating roles of psychological contract fulfilment between the relationship of abusive supervision and employees organizational citizenship behaviors. Furthermore, the results of the current study also suggests an important role of trust in leader as a boundary specificity of the relationship between abusive supervision and organizational citizenship behaviors. At the end, this research presents several important implications, which truly enrich our understanding regarding abusive supervision and employees organizational citizenship behaviors.

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Introduction

A substantial number of studies have been conducted on organizational citizenship behavior (hereafter OCB); however, there is still an ample of research gaps in the present literature that need scholarly attention to build further the theory and literature of organizational behavior and OCB. Specifically, from the extensive leadership literature search of this study, it has been found out that there are many leadership paradigms, but only a few of them were researched for establishing relationship with OCB. For example, previous researches only established six leadership paradigms as having links with OCB. The leadership paradigms consist of: (1) transformational leadership (Kim and Park, 2019) (2) charismatic leadership (Babcock-Roberson, and Strickland, 2010) (3) transactional leadership (Tremblay and Gibson, 2016) (4) ethical leadership (Piccolo et al., 2010) (5) and, servant leadership (Walumbwa, Hartnell, and Oke, 2010) etc. Considering the extant leadership approaches reported in the leadership literature, there is a need for OCB research to explore its possible relationships with various unexplored leadership styles. Specifically, this study presents abusive supervision and their relationships with some employee outcomes, i.e. organization citizenship behaviors. Largely, the contribution made by this study did not exist in the extant leadership literature.

In total, the current study present several implications. Along with certain managerial implications for organizations, our research also add theoretical implications to the existing literature. For instance, based on social exchange view (Blau, 1964), our study explore the relationship between abusive supervision, and employees OCBs. Further, psychological contract fulfilment is suggested to mediate the abusive supervision and employees OCBs relationship. In addition, trust in leadership is expected to moderate the relationship between abusive supervision and employees OCBs. This study add to both theoretical and practical significance into the contemporary literature on leadership and OCB. The existing theory on employees' OCBs is examined and tested in a new cultural context, Morocco. It is because; Morocco has a very different cultural setting compared to developed nations, where the conception of employee OCBs has been developed. To contemporary researchers, it is imperative to conduct studies across various cultures to compare results in order to generate sound understanding, particularly for a comparatively novel concept like employee's OCBs. For example, Hofstede (2006) emphasize that management scientists are human beings, and they cannot develop a theory without accepting impact of culture in which they live. Thus, there is a need to study various aspects of management in different cultural contexts. In addition, although employee's OCBs is a topic that has been increasingly investigated from both practical and academic perspectives in the West, its relationships with various key leadership styles is still unclear in most of the other countries, especially in Morocco. More specifically, little is known empirically about how different leadership styles, such as abusive supervision, may relate to the development of employee OCBs. Thus, a study aiming on the association of abusive supervision and employee's OCBs, while also considering some potential moderator and mediator could add needed knowledge to the leadership and OCB conceptualizations.

Theoretical Underpinning

Social Exchange Theory

Social exchange theory (SET; Blau, 1964) is considered as one of the most prominent theories in context of organizational behavior, and it is the most important conceptual paradigm to study workplace behavior (Cropanzano and Mitchel, 2005). Blau (1964) emphasized the significance of social exchange among individuals beyond economic advantages, while Emerson (1976) posit that the major features of SET are interaction among individuals and

the subsequent generation of obligations. Social exchange theory offers a theoretical basis to recognize the structural associations among each of the variables (abusive supervision, psychological contract fulfillment, and OCB). Social exchange could occur when both parties exchange something based on mutual trust (Blau, 1964). This theory conceptualizes the relationship between employees and organizations (or leaders) (Settoon et al., 1996). Similarly, in exchange of services of employees for the organization, the employers should take care of employees (Cropanzano and Mitchell, 2005). According to Eisenberger et al., (1990), individuals' attitude toward their employer/organization is determined by their perception on leadership behaviors. For example, when employees recognize organizational fairness in their organization, they will likely try to reciprocate with a positive work attitude (Aryee et al., 2002). On the other hand, toxic leader's behavior has been shown detrimental consequences for both organizations and employees (for example, see Rafferty and Restubog, 2011; Wu and Lee, 2016).

Figure 1 Proposed Model

Abusive leadership and employees OCBs

Abusive supervision refers to a subcategory of toxic leadership styles, and has been term as “subordinates’ perceptions of the extent to which their supervisors engage in the sustained display of hostile verbal and nonverbal behaviors, excluding physical contact” Tepper (2000; p. 178). Harvey et al. (2007), defined abusive supervision as representing the prolonged emotional or psychological maltreatment of individuals. For instance abusive behaviors include public ridicule, taking undue credit, invasion of privacy, wrongly assigning blame, breaking promises, inconsiderate actions, rudeness, the silent treatment, mocking employees in front of colleagues, withholding vital information, & the use of disparaging language. Supervisors in organizations have the potential to negatively or positively affect individual’s behaviors, attitudes, and their over-all well-being within workplace context (Michel et al., 2016). Prior studies have examined the deleterious effects of abusive supervision on individual and organizations alike. Abusive supervision has been found to be significantly correlated with various undesired outcomes. For example, employee strain (Huo et al., 2012), psychological distress (Wu and Lee, 2016), work-family conflict (Tepper, 2000), low organizational commitment (Aryee et al., 2007), lower performance (Shoss et al., 2013), lower employee creativity (Liu et al., 2016) and increased counterproductive work behaviors,

turnover intentions, & knowledge hiding (Ghani et al., 2020; Detert et al., 2007; Martinko et al., 2013). Similarly, employees who feel abusive supervision tend to sense undervalued and view themselves as social outcasts in the workplace setting (Michel et al., 2016). Hence, we presume that in the presence of abusive leadership behaviors, the employees feelings that the organization is “theirs” may no longer exist and they will respond in retaliatory way and will disowned their organizations. Consequently, individuals might start to illustrate amplified negative work behaviors and reduced OCB, s (Martinko et al., 2013).

H1: *Abusive leadership is significantly negatively related to employees OCBs.*

Abusive leadership, psychological contract fulfilment, and employees OCBs

Cognitions of PC fulfillment are consider representative of perceived balance in the exchange association between an employee and her/his organization. Following from the norm of reciprocity and, SET (Blau, 1964), we expected that employees who observed balance in the employee–organization (i.e., leaders) exchange association would feel an obligation to continue to involve in behaviors that were favorable to the organization. Hence, in parallel with prior studies (Turnley, Bolino, Lester, and Bloodgood, 2003), it is suggested that involvement by employees in OCB, s would be equivalent to their perceptions of the organization’s/employer fulfillment of its obligations towards them. Prior studies have examined the harmful influence of supervisory abusive on organizations and individual alike. Supervisory abusive has been argued to be significantly and positively associated with various undesired outcomes. For example, employee strain (Huo et al., 2012), psychological distress (Wu and Lee, 2016), work–family conflict (Tepper, 2000), job satisfaction, organizational commitment (Aryee et al., 2007), lower task, contextual performance (Shoss et al., 2013), lower employee creativity (Liu et al., 2016) and increased counterproductive work behaviors, turnover intentions, & knowledge hiding (Ghani et al., 2020; Detert et al., 2007; Martinko et al., 2013). Similarly, employees who experience supervisory abusive may feel undervalued and view themselves as social outcasts in the workplace setting (Michel et al., 2016). Hence, we presume that in the presence of abusive leadership behaviors, the employees’ feelings that the organization no longer fulfilled their promises which will arose the perceptions of psychological breach instead of PC fulfilment. This line of argument is also echoed by prior studies, for example, Morsch, van Dijk, and Kodden (2020), argued that leaders abusiveness leads towards certain unfavorable attitudinal outcomes for individuals. Consequently, employees might begin to display more negative work behaviors and lower in OCB, s (Martinko et al., 2013).

The association between abusive supervision, employee’s PC fulfilment, and employees OCB can be better explained with the help of SET. SET reveals that employees form, sustain, or dismiss relations in the workplaces “on the basis of the perceived ratio of benefits to costs in the relationship” (Ensher, Thomas, and Murphy, 2001, p. 421). Social exchange can happen in relations where both parties anticipate a long time association and have a mutual trust toward each other (Cropanzano and Mitchell, 2005). In terms of employee OCB, once employees perceive fair treatment and the association is not limited to economic exchange but contains sincere organization or leadership support and vice versa. In the presence of abusive supervision, employees as a reciprocity will likely to think the organization were failed to fulfilled the promises been made and choose to be not engaged in extra-job & organizational activities as a retaliation. Based on the above-mentioned literature and theoretical support we suppose the following hypotheses.

H2: *Psychological contract fulfilment mediates the relationship between abusive leadership and employees OCBs.*

Moderating role of trust in leader between abusive supervision & employees OCBs

Trust has been conceptualized as a center of attraction in social sciences (Terri, Scandura, and Pellegrini, 2008), due of its significance for sustaining organizational effectiveness. Trust is term as “willingness to depend on another party” (Mayer, Davis, and Schoorman, 1995). The most frequently used conceptualization of trust (Mayer et al., 1995) is “willingness to be vulnerable” (712). According to Rousseau et al. (1998) “Trust is a psychological state comprising the intention to accept vulnerability based on positive expectations of the intentions or behavior of another”. Leader-member exchange (LMX) view of leadership underlines on the two-way association between leaders and followers and highlights trust as an important condition for a social exchanges in the workplaces (Konovsky and Pugh, 1994). In this way for LMX trust is considered to be an essential factor (Schriesheim, Castro, and Cogliser, 1999). Leaders offer direction to their followers as “people turn to personal relationships for guidance, and the quality of these relationships is mainly determined by the level of trust” (Otken and Cenkci, 2012). Talking about trust in leader (Atkinson and Butcher, 2003), it is “to place oneself in a position of personal risk based on expectations that the trustee (leader) will not behave in a way those results in harm to the trustor (subordinate)” (p. 289).

It is the trust that binds the employees to his/her supervisor so the supervisors has to be trusted by his subordinates (Nanus, 1989). This is extremely significant because only then the employees will go for additional effort for effective performance in the workplaces. For example, to exhibit high levels positive outcomes from individuals such as satisfaction, commitment and efficient performance needs trust in their leadership (Bartram and Casimir, 2007). Posner and Schmidts (1984) argued that “trustworthiness and honesty” are considered the most vital characteristics for a leader (Frost and Moussavi, 1999). An organization effectiveness of can be recognized by effective leadership and mutual trust between leaders and subordinates is important to build strong association among them (Otken and Cenkci, 2012). Furthermore, the trust between an employees and his/her leader is considered a major factor in collectivist culture setting (Ertürk, 2008). As a whole, trust in leader greatly affect positive leadership styles to develop the clear perceptions regarding the organizational practices (Otken and Cenkci, 2012). Janowicz-Panjaitan and Krishnan (2009) inspected organizational trust as a form of attribution theory, such that employees will make a sense of their environments whether negative or positive based on the association they have with the organization. Therefore, individuals with high degree of organizational trust are more comfortable taking risks, performing behaviors for the organization, and displaying ideas (Altinkurt and Yilmaz, 2011). From this perspective, employees that display high levels of organization trust can be expected to display behaviors that go above and beyond that which is expected of them (Altinkurt and Yilmaz, 2011). To sum up, based on the prior study’s findings that trust in the leader enhances satisfaction, commitment, and performance, we assume that trust in the leader may also influence employees OCBs (Tourigny et al., 2019) in the presence of various leadership styles. Therefore, based on aforementioned literature, and theoretical arguments, we propose that in the presence of abusive supervision, the employees trust in leader varyingly influence on the behavioral outcomes such as, organizational citizenship behaviors. Hence, we hypothesize the following:

H3: *Trust in leader moderates the association between abusive supervision and OCBs, such that the relationship is weaker for those higher in trust in leadership and higher for those lower in trust in leadership.*

Methodology

Data were collected from 436 respondents to test the proposed model. We contacted 646 full-time employees working in Morocco's agriculture sector organizations. A structured questionnaire was used and asked the participant to fill in three points in time, with a time lag of one month. In Time 1, questionnaires were distributed among 646 respondents, consisted demographics and abusive supervision items. We get back 509 responses at point one. After an interval of one month, the questionnaires were distributed among those who responded in Time 1, including trust in leader and psychological contract breach items, and get back 475 responses in Time 2. Finally, in Time 3, the questionnaires were distributed to those who responded in Time 2, and received 448 responses back. The average time for completing each questionnaire (in Time 1, Time 2, and Time 3) was about 15 minutes. The participants selected anonymous and a unique identifier to Time 1, Time 2, and Time 3 responses and make sure the anonymity. We collected 448 response but after checking for missing data, 12 questionnaire were found which are not properly filled or having misleading information's. Therefore, we remove those questionnaire and the valid 436 questionnaires were used for analysis. The response rate of valid questionnaires to initially distributed questionnaires was 69.34%. The participant's demographic information are mentioned below in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Categories		Frequency	%age
Age (in years)	<25	113	25.9
	25-33	233	53.4
	34-42	74	17.0
	>42	16	3.7
Gender	Male	203	46.6
	Female	233	53.4
Qualification	SSC or below	23	5.3
	Bachelor	192	44.0
	Masters	173	39.7
	Others	48	11.0
Experience (in years)	<1	59	13.5
	1-5	162	37.2
	6-10	110	25.2
	11-15	47	10.8
	>15	58	13.3

Scales

Abusive supervision

A shortened five items scale was used from Peng, Schaubroeck and Li (2014) to measure employees the abusive behaviors of their supervisors. We asked employees to report the frequency with which their immediate supervisors exhibit various hostile acts to them. One example item include "My supervisor tells me my thoughts & feelings are stupid" and My supervisor puts me down in front of others.

Psychological contract fulfillment

Psychological contract fulfillment was measure on 4-items scale adapted from the study of Henderson, Wayne, Shore, Bommer, and Tetrick, (2008). Sample items are "My Company has often broken promises made to me (reverse coded)" and "My Company considering the promises that has made to me".

Trust in leader

Trust in leader was assessed using seven items scale from Podsakoff et al., (1990). Example items are "I feel a strong loyalty to my leader" "I have complete faith in the integrity of my leader".

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

OCB was measured using Lee and Allen's (2002) Organizational Citizenship Behavior Scale. This 16-item scale includes two subscales measuring interpersonal and organizational directed organizational citizenship behaviors. Participants was rated how often they engage in certain behaviors.

Measurement model

Prior to testing our hypotheses, CFA was performed to examine the validity of the study constructs. CFA is essential when the data are collected from the same source. The CFA results demonstrates good model fitness indices for the measurement model ($\chi^2 = 1330.293$, d.f. = 451, $p = 0.000$, CFI = 0.929, RMSEA = 0.067, RMR = 0.074) (Hu and Bentler, 1999). The loadings items fit the model well, as the values were above the suggested cut-off score of 0.70. Further, to test convergent validity, we measured the Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE) scores to demonstrate how items are inter-related (see Table 2). The Cronbach's alpha were greater than the cut-off value of 0.70. Likewise, the CR and AVE values ranged from 0.905 to 0.960 and 0.601 to 0.820 and were significantly higher than the benchmark value of 0.70 and 0.50 respectively, showing accepted convergent validity of the measurement model. To ensure discriminant validity, two conditions should be fulfilled. First, the inter-construct correlations should not exceed the benchmark score of 0.85, and second, the AVE square root should load higher than the constructs correlations (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). As shown in Table 3, the measurement model fulfilled these prerequisite, hence, discriminant validity was satisfied. Taken together, the hypothesized model possessed satisfactory reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity.

Table2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Variables	Items	Factor Loadings	CA	CR	AVE
Abusive Supervision	ABS1	.747	.904	.905	.657
	ABS2	.811			
	ABS3	.829			
	ABS4	.865			
	ABS5	.795			
Trust in Leader	TL1	.893	.943	.943	.704
	TL2	.907			
	TL3	.897			
	TL4	.811			
	TL5	.826			
	TL6	.738			
	TL7	.785			
Psychological Contract Fulfillment	PCF1	.848	.950	.948	.820
	PCF2	.835			
	PCF3	.946			
	PCF4	.984			
Organization Citizenship Behavior	OCB1	.704	.960	.960	.601
	OCB2	.779			
	OCB3	.788			
	OCB4	.766			
	OCB5	.751			
	OCB6	.770			
	OCB7	.789			
	OCB8	.790			
	OCB9	.764			
	OCB10	.785			
	OCB11	.756			
	OCB12	.825			
	OCB13	.816			
	OCB14	.796			
	OCB15	.805			
	OCB16	.709			

Note: CA=Cronbach's Alpha, CR=Composite Reliability, AVE= Average Variance Extracted

Hypotheses testing

The means, standardized deviations (SD), and Pearson’s correlation coefficients of all the study constructs are reported in Table 3. All the relationships were in expected directions.

Table 3: Means, Standard Deviations and Correlations

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1.Gender	1.53	.49	1							
2.Age	1.98	.76	-.123*	1						
3.Education	2.56	.75	-.149**	.056	1					
4.Experience	2.73	1.21	.010	.045	.037	1				
5.ABS	3.57	1.42	-.125**	-.100*	.036	-.059	.810			
6.TL	4.99	1.54	-.014	.015	.038	.089	-.259**	.839		
7.PCF	4.74	1.58	.026	-.008	-.013	.062	-.344**	.170**	.905	
8.OCB	4.84	1.34	.018	-.026	-.028	.044	-.438**	.367**	.462**	.775

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). ABS=Abusive Supervision, TL=Trust in Leader, PCF=Psychological Contract Fulfillment, OCB=Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

We employed the macro devised by Hayes (2012) in SPSS to check the direct and indirect effect between the predictor variable (abusive supervision) and the outcome (organizational citizenship behavior) through the mediators (psychological contract fulfillment). The results of the test of the direct relationships (H1) as well as indirect effect (H2, H3) are illustrated in Table 4. Results reveal a negative relationship between abusive supervision and organizational citizenship behavior ($\beta = -.415$, $SE = .04$, $p < .01$), supporting H1. The mediating effect of psychological contract fulfillment between abusive supervision and organizational contract fulfillment was significant (indirect effect = $-.115$, $Boot SE = .024$; 95%, CI $\{-.056, -.121\}$), thus, H2 supported.

Table 4. Mediation effect

Outcome: organizational citizenship behavior	β	SE	t	R ²
				.192
Constant	6.324**	.157	40.2630	
Abusive supervision	-.415**	.041	-10.155	
Outcome: Psychological contract fulfillment	β	SE	t	R ²
				.119
Constant	6.110**	.193	31.699	
Abusive supervision	-.383**	.050	-7.641	
Outcome: Organizational citizenship behavior	β	SE	t	R ²
				.302
Constant	4.487**	.267	16.862	
Psychological contract fulfillment	.301**	.036	8.257	
Abusive supervision	-.299**	.041	-7.402	
	Effect	SE	LL 95% CI	UL 95 % CI
Indirect effect	-.115	.024	-.121	-.056
	Effect	SE	z	
Normal theory test for indirect effect	-.115	.020	-5.5860	

Note: ** $p < .01$, Bootstrap sample size= 5000, CI= confident interval, LU= lower limit, UL= upper limit.

To examine hypothesis 3, employees trust in leader moderate the negative relationship between abusive supervision and organizational citizenship behavior. As shown in Table 5, the interaction term (abusive supervision x trust in leader) was statistically significant ($\beta = -.057$, $p < .05$), demonstrating that trust in leader moderates the abusive supervision-

organizational citizenship behavior relationship (H3 supported). Furthermore, Figure 2 depict that how trust in leader (at high and low levels) moderated the abusive supervision and organizational citizenship behavior.

Table 5 Moderation effect

Outcome: Organizational citizenship behavior	β	SE	t	R ²
Constant	4.809**	.062	77.608	.269
Abusive supervision	-.339**	.053	-6.441	
Trust in leader	.258**	.046	5.644	
Abusive supervision x trust in leader	-.057*	.035	-2.652	

Note: ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$, Bootstrap sample= 5000.

Figure 2 Moderation effect of trust in leader

Discussion

To promote employees organizations citizenship behaviors, the current study developed a model that combine abusive supervision, psychological contract fulfilment, trust in leaders, and organizations citizenship behaviors. We targeted Morocco's agriculture sector employees to collect data and test the causal relationships among the various study variables. Our findings reveals that how abusive supervision declining employees organization citizenship behaviors, which underscore the importance of several underlying mechanisms. Specifically, this research focuses on the intervening variables i.e., psychological contract fulfilment, which clarifies how abusive supervision translates into employees citizenship behaviors. Moreover, to further clarify the relationship between abusive supervision and outcomes, the present study considers one important variable i.e., trust in leader. The results indicate that trust in leaders from individuals further strengthen the negative relationship between abusive supervision and employees OCB's. In below we discussed the current research implications for theory and practice.

Theoretical Implications

The present study adds to the literature on leadership and OCBs. First, the study builds a link between the literature on abusive supervision and employees OCB's. The study results shows

that negative leader's behaviors (i.e., abusive supervision) affect employee's citizenship behaviors negatively. The findings have confirmed the primary viewpoint that leaders' support/undermine can stimulate employees' citizenship behaviors (Chiaburu, Peng, Oh, Banks, and Lomeli, 2013). Gregory, Osmonbekov, Gregory, Albritton, and Carr (2002), finding that abusive supervision is negatively linked to individuals citizenship behaviors, was unable to be replicated employing a Morocco based sample. Noticeably, employees' reactions to supervisory abusive could be at variance by national culture, as some cultures are more accepting of social inequity than others. Moreover, given certain cultural settings (Hofstede, Bond, and Luk, 1993), employees may be unfamiliar to questioning his/her superior's behaviors and might be hesitant to withhold their own positive discretionary behaviors because of fear of supervisor retaliation. Morocco has been shown to be higher in power distance than the Western countries, meaning that Moroccan employees are likely more tolerant of negative supervisor behaviors than their counterparts. Second, the current study contributes to both the antecedents and outcomes psychological contract fulfilment. Negative leaders are assumed to accelerate unfavorable outcomes. In consistent with SET (Blau, 1964) and conservation of resource perspective (Hobfoll, 1989), our results demonstrate that in the presence of supervisory abuse individuals are more likely to withhold the ownership perceptions, and ultimately, would not engage in organization citizenship behaviors.

Perceptions of psychological contract fulfillment are considered representative of perceived balance in the exchange relationship between an individual and her/his organization. Following from the norm of reciprocity and, SET (Blau, 1964), our findings confirmed that employees who observed balance in the employee-organization (i.e., leaders) exchange relationship would feel an obligation to continue to involve in behaviors that were favorable to the organization i.e., citizenship behaviors. Whereas, by expanding the previous work (Tepper, 2000; Aryee et al., 2007), our research further clarifies that why and how negative leaders behaviors (i.e., abusive supervision) negatively affects employees OCBs. Third, our study contribute to the important role of trust in leader in the association between various abusive supervision and employees OCB's. The findings confirmed that trust in leader work as a positive moderator between abusive supervision, and OCBs. Likewise, the results shows that in time of abusive leadership, employees trust in leader helps individuals to mitigate this impact on their OCBs. Furthermore, the trust between the employee and his supervisor is considered an important factor in collectivist culture (Ertürk, 2008). Therefore, this study adds to the discussion on cultural perspective while developing and testing our model based on a sample from one of the collectivist society.

Practical Implications

The results of this research might have practical implications for organizations. First, organizations should be aware of the injurious influence of supervisory abusive. Our study reveals that supervisory abusive was positively related to psychological contract fulfilment, which subsequently contributed to lower employees OCB. Hence, we propose that organizations should take counter measures to mitigate the intensity of abusive supervision in the workplaces. For instance, scholars have provided an initial confirmation regarding the role of self-control capacity in regulating abusive behaviors from supervisors (Mawritz, Greenbaum, Butts, and Graham, 2017). In this line, organizations need to consider selecting individuals with high degree of self-control as team supervisors. Given that individuals tend to view their leaders as organizational representatives (Aselage and Eisenberger, 2003), when leaders are believed to be acting morally and ethically, employees are likely in turn experience more pride and satisfaction to work for their organization.

Moreover, organizations might organize leadership training programs on regular basis to help leaders to adopt and learn more effective interpersonal tactics when interacting with employees at workplaces. For instance, organizations can organize emotional intelligence training programs to develop negative supervisors to listen to their follower ideas, be compassionate to employees emotions, and offer greater support when needed (Goleman, Boyatzis, and McKee, 2002). This kind of leadership interventions can increase leader-member exchange associations and enable organizational commitment with the organizations (Liden, Wayne, Zhao, and Henderson, 2008). Our findings reinforce the notion that social stressors are the important drivers of numerous harmful outcomes (Harris, Harvey, and Kacmar, 2009). Recently scholars have well noted that work stressors are frequently happening in the workplaces (Mackey, Frieder, Brees, and Martinko, 2017), organizations could seek ways to minimize the amount of abusive behaviors in the work settings. Given the destructive effects of abusive supervision in the work context, decision makers need to promote positive social work climates and also establish norms against any type of aggression and injustice occurrences. Consequently, it is more likely that perceptions of ownership and psychological contract fulfilment would arise, ultimate will motivate individuals to engage in organization citizenship behaviors.

Limitations of the Study

Several significant limitations were likely in the current research. First, the present study relied on prior developed and validated tools that were initially formed in the Western context. We realize that the substantial dissimilarities between the developed nations and Morocco, where this research took place, could be anticipated to happen. Secondly, another limitation of the study is specially related to the procedure followed for instrument translation. To previous research findings (Yu, Lee, and Woo, 2004) employing the same instrument in diverse studies facilitates comparison across different culture settings. Nevertheless, the instrument used must be translated correctly so that the reliabilities and validities of the scales still exist in its true meaning (Yaghi, Goodman, Holton, and Bates, 2008). Even though all required steps were executed to make sure the inclusiveness of the translation, it is nearly impossible for the translation procedure to yield perfectly the similar meanings from two various languages. For example, Yu et al. (2004) summarized the problems of translation they encountered in their study, such as a huge difference in cultural experiences with a certain concept as well as dissimilarities in grammatical and syntactical styles of the target and original languages. These issues were also expected to happen in the translation of instruments in this research study. Third, as data were collected through self-reported questionnaire, the use of self-reported data is another limitation of our study. The major disadvantage of self-reported data collection occurs when respondents provide socially desirable responses in order to increase their chance of viewing noble in other people's eyes (O'Driscoll, Pierce, and Coghlan, 2006; Barrick, Mount, and Judge, 2001). Similarly, survey was conducted based on "voluntary response," i.e., the participants were self-selected, and they contributed in responding the survey questions voluntarily because they have strong opinions, and thus overstated their answers. Though significant efforts have been done to reduce the potential selection bias, i.e., by briefing the participants on the significance of the information they provided, they may have given the same response related to predictor and outcome variables. This may cause biases in response because the same employee was providing information concerning their own employer and, because of their affiliation to their employer, it may have led them to either underestimate or overestimate their responses. Though this research guaranteed participants privacy, it is unlikely to have fully excluded all aspects of social desirability in answers.

Fourthly, it is to be expected that this research study would have shortcomings in terms of the potential moderator considered. This study concentrated on selected crucial factor directly linked to the field of human resource management and organization behavior. However, several variables influencing the association between leadership styles and employees OCB, such as individual's personality and other contextual factors, were not considered in the study, which might also play an important role in this relationship. Finally, one limitation of this research was the generalizability of the findings. The samples in this study were taken from organizations related to agriculture sector, hence cannot be applied to other work settings. Care must be particularly taken to generalize the results beyond these settings.

Recommendations for Further Research

Based on the aforementioned findings and limitations of this study, future researchers should consider expanding on this study in several ways. Firstly, as organizations need more citizenship behaviors, more studies are required on several other leadership styles (such as servant leadership, leader member exchange, transaction leadership and, inclusive leadership) in relationship with OCB, s. This will surely help the organizations to compare the various leadership approaches and will able to choose the best leadership in order to stimulate more individuals for exhibiting extra citizenship behaviors in the work organizations. Second, we tested for an important underlying mechanisms psychological contract fulfilment in the relationship between abusive supervision and employees OCB's, which proves its potential for translating the influence of leadership styles on OCBs. Further studies need to comprehend the current model by considering numerous individuals level intervening factors. Third, we investigated one important moderation variable (i.e., trust in leader) in the relationship between leadership styles and employees OCBs. Future research may build upon our theoretical model to unearth the moderating influence of several individual personality dimensions and contextual factors that might strengthen or mitigate the leadership styles and OCB relationship. In addition, the role of national culture in shaping leader behaviors, effectiveness, and attributes are a long-standing issue of the organizational studies (House Wright and Aditya, 1997). Mostly leading management concepts and theories, included leadership, were largely developed in the developed nations (Bass, 1985). Nevertheless, management practices and the means in which leaders are viewed by subordinates relatively vary widely from one country to another (Hofstede et al., 1993), in part due to the influence of national culture on individuals expectations of work, supervisors and structure of the organizations (Triandis, 1993). It is therefore critical to investigate whether or not a leadership theory pioneered in the developed culture generalizes well to other countries by examining the current model in other countries context.

Likewise, recently noted by Lu, Xie, & Gua. (2018), "in current organizational and management research, one of the main missions is to delineate boundary conditions of a certain theory or studied phenomenon (p. 187)." Previous studies in the leadership domain has advocated the investigation of how personality characteristics may influence individuals' perceptions and responses to various leadership approaches (Antonakis et al., 2012). Hence, we suggest future scholars to explore different personality traits as a boundary specificity in the relationship between leadership styles and individuals OCB, s. Finally, as noted above, the samples in this study were taken from organizations related to agriculture sector, hence cannot be applied to other work organizations. To further enrich the theoretical and practical implications of the current study, we suggest that future studies should replicate the current model in other work settings.

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